

BEGINNING STAGE OF LEARNING TO PLAY THE CELLO

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Abstract: In this article, an attempt is made to consider the process of the initial stage of learning to play the cello. Special attention was paid to the problems of mastering the musical instrument by young cellists.

Key words: cello, music education, student development, culture, instrument performance, art.

Introduction.

The initial stage of learning to play the cello is one of the most difficult periods in the life of any young musician. As a rule, this stage corresponds to preschool and primary school age. It is at this age that the formation of a person, his socialization, the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, as well as the first experience on the path of a great creative life, take place.

At the same time, cellists studying in various additional educational institutions during their childhood face special difficulties. In addition to receiving basic basic education, they also have to learn to play a musical instrument - the cello, which is undoubtedly an additional emotional burden that significantly affects the emotional and emotional development of students.

In general, the question of internal development of cellists of such a young age is not only theoretical, but also practical. The answers and conclusions obtained during this article allow solving all problems related to the formation of a full-fledged personality of future musicians, as well as contribute to their development in the process of professional musical activity.

It should be noted that there is a large amount of scientific and practical literature on the above issue, which undoubtedly once again confirms the relevance of the chosen topic. The writing of this article is related to the need not only to revise the existing performance methods and methods, but also to develop new scientifically based methods related to learning to play the cello.

Nowadays, the question of the initial stage of learning to play the cello is still acute. Despite the fact that many works were written, for example: K. Yu. Davydov, J. L. Dupor, F. Dotzauer, M. Korret's "Violin School". The question remains relevant to this day. Each teacher chooses his own, unique approach and teaching methodology. In working with students, the psychological aspect, the ability to establish communication and interest the future cellist is

important. The student's physical profile remains equally important. At the initial stage of teaching, the teacher should immediately pay attention to the following information of the student: flexibility of fingers, coordination of movements, musical hearing, rhythm, etc. Even if the ear for music is in the right shape, it can be developed, but at the same time maximum care and work on oneself is necessary. Rhythm is a prerequisite for anyone who wants to succeed in music.

It should be noted that the cello has always played a special role in the formation of musical culture. Cello is often compared to the human voice. The emotional power of cello works is clearly described by Gorky in his autobiographical novel People. In pedagogy, the history of cello art is an integral part, it is the only process of development of performance and literature. All the above aspects required the examination of certain factors in pedagogy, their re-evaluation and revision from the point of view of modern musicology. The study, formation and development of pedagogy will undoubtedly help to solve a number of problems that are relevant for modern cello culture. In addition, the study of the history of cello art fills the general picture of the historical development of modern musical culture as a whole.

The importance of the first elementary practical steps in the important process of learning to play the cello can be overstated. The habits of students that appear in the initial period of education definitely affect the further development of the student. Beginning cello playing, for example, the way a student holds the instrument before starting to play with a bow, are both good and bad possibilities. There is no other tool that requires maximum accuracy and coordination of movements during the previous training period. At the same time, the correct way to hold the instrument takes place before all further development of the student.

During the education of the child, the teacher should carefully monitor the development of the student. This is a big responsibility and the result that comes from it. The teacher develops in the child a musical ear, a sense of rhythm, as well as an artistic idea about the nature and style of the works that will take place in the classroom with the child. The great role of the teacher corresponds to the initial stage of education. During this period, the basis of musical and artistic performances and the basics of instrument ownership were created. A teacher working with children must have a plan for working with a student, taking into account his characteristics and individual abilities. From the first lessons, you should teach the child to listen to what they are playing, to control

the quality of the voice, to strive for free movements of the hands and to constantly monitor the intonation. The main task of the teacher is to correctly and clearly explain the technique of playing with the help of demonstration on the instrument or figurative explanations. The quality of the classes and the rapid transition to more complex techniques will depend on it.

It is necessary to educate the student: perseverance, endurance, the ability to quickly solve executive tasks, perseverance in achieving the goal. It is necessary to explain to the teacher how to organize daily homework, taking into account the individual data and the time that the student can devote to them.

Getting to know the instrument is always a very exciting process for both the student and the teacher. The teacher should play the instrument to show the beauty of the sound, the unusual timbre of the instrument. It makes a bright impression on the student and helps to get acquainted with the instrument faster.

Before starting to play the instrument, it is necessary to perform a series of exercises that will help you master the instrument. You need to get a pencil or stick, on which to practice the first skills of holding a bow. Then introduce the details of the instrument and tell how the open threads are named. The instrument and bow should be selected taking into account the growth and physical condition of the student. You should take care in advance about the presence of a footrest or a small chair.

First of all, every beginning cellist should remember that we have three points of support when playing and interacting: the spine, the chest, and the left knee. You just need to take the edge of the chair and sit on the chair in half of it. The back should be straight, the body slightly bent forward. The legs should be placed with the whole leg.

Classes should be built from simple to complex, choosing simple works first, achieving small successes, moving on to more complex works. For the gradual mastery of the instrument, cellist-pedagogues have specially developed "chrestomatias" for beginners, for example: L. Marderovsky, R. Sapojnikov, I. Volchkov. It is very important that the lessons are conducted in a positive way so that the student can quickly learn the necessary skills and adapt to the tool.

Before children start playing an instrument, it is necessary to develop the skills of emotional response and perception of music. The teacher should gradually develop the students' skills in singing, choosing melodies, listening, learning musical notes, using exercises that help to loosen the playing apparatus.

Conclusion.

As mentioned above, the topic of this article has been the subject of scientific research several times before. However, time is passing, generations of cellists are changing, new methods and methods of teaching are emerging, and modern trends are emerging. Therefore, in the near future, there may be a need to develop and formulate new teaching methods, while this article will be used both for theoretical studies in the future and practical application of the necessary skills at the initial stage of learning to play the cello.

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